

Teaching English language for the blind

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ABSTRACT

English language is an international language used in order to communicate in the fields of education, technology, trade and politics so that it is learnt by not only sighted people, but also the blind. The article mainly focuses on instructing English language for sightless individuals. The researcher suggested her own strategies and data that she collected. The main part of the article consists of tips of educating English language for unsighted people. Keywords: globalization, verbal memory, brain, rich understanding, instructors, touch screens with voice, MP3 players, screen readers. Introduction. Globalization has grown significantly, more and more the blind want to communicate with foreigners, to travel to overseas or just to enjoy various types of social situations. In any of these cases, the English learners who are blind should motivate to acquire a knowledge of English language, although they cannot see.

Main body. There are myriad kinds of strategies in order to educate the blind. Touch screens with voice, MP3 players, screen readers are excited example of this. Classroom activities that include physical artifacts or music enable students to take in the language with their other senses. 1. "It's interesting that people who are blind only showed an advantage with verbal memory". Researchers conducted two memory tests with 20 blind adults and 22 blindfolded sighted adults. They wondered if blind participants would outperform sighted ones at remembering spoken sounds. First, participants listened to series of letters followed by a delay. Then they heard either the same series or a "fail" series where a letter is replaced or put into the wrong position. Participants then judged whether the second series of letters was the same as the first. For the second test, they listened to letters while solving mathematical equations with proposed answers. Participants determined if equations solutions were correct, followed by reciting back the letters 2. Actually, touch screens, MP3 players and screen readers help to learn English for the blind. In order to do these, qualified instructors should record grammar structures, vocabularies and so on And also, they do every activity with a blind person who is learning English language. Instructors should be qualified when they teach English for the blind. Because the blind come across some problems during lessons and they question a lot. "Talk to students a lot, even though they may not always understand. After a while they will. Speak in complete sentences 3. Instructors are essential for the blind to learn

English. Therefore, it is chosen qualified instructors to teach English language. The instructors be careful during lesson, as the blind cannot see anything, so they are good at receiving information Talking a lot students helps to improve the quality of teaching English language for the blind. "On a daily basis, blind people use their memory much more to remember things, while sighted people can rely on visual clues to recall information" 4.By listening MP3 players, screen readers and touch sceens with voice, blind people can learn English easily. As, they hear everything and try to remember. Really, it's the best way to learn foreign language. The blind hear lessons be active to memorize new things and attentive all things while listening audio books. "Blind people cannot seecolor but understand it the same way as sighted"5

According to this theory,large wall charts are benefcial to teach English for the blind.Conclusion. Teaching English for the blind can be very rewarding,however very dificult as well.Teaching English is a challenge for both teachers and learners.Nevertheless,both parties should work hard.Blind people should be provided with all the devices to organize the English language.By creating these facilities,the blind can organize easily English language.

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